

Convening for a Cause Workshop

How can we solve the biggest nutrient problem – iron deficiency?

Workshop goals

Gather multiple stakeholders and partners to:

- Better understand the factors that influence the success of interventions for the treatment and prevention of iron deficiency (ID) and iron deficiency anemia (IDA)
- Map a co-designed system for improved family health through treatment and prevention of ID/IDA

Who was there?

1 community catalyst

7 government ministries

4 public health & medical experts

11 health researchers

Capstone National Meeting:
Oct 5, 2023
Cotonou, Benin

4 NGOs

6 social enterprises/businesses

2 embassy representatives

3 experts by experience

Emerging insights

1. Purpose, priorities and goals

Accessible nutrition interventions for all communities and life stages

Equal opportunities to access interventions for all communities, that consider social norms and religious beliefs

Promote education on the use of the Fish and iron-rich foods to **increase use**

Develop a sustainable roadmap to implement an accessible intervention to treat and prevent ID

2. Resources needed to achieve the priorities

Financial resources

Human resources

Knowledge promotion resources

Policy and protocols resources

3. Activities/products that can support the goals

Commitment from key stakeholders to the cause

Coordination among sectors to deploy a cohesive approach

Engagement with community leaders and health sectors to **advocate** for use of the Fish

Synthesise and disseminate evidence to support future nutrition programmes

NEXT STEPS

- Analysis of discussions from the workshop and community engagement meetings
- Draft roadmaps to share with attendees, with the goal of collectively developing an implementation plan
- Search for resources to fund future activities towards improving nutrition and reducing ID/IDA in Benin

Learn more: www.beninwithoutirondeficiency.com

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